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Teachers' Continuous Education Management For Enhanced Instructional Delivery In Public Secondary Schools In River State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions were answered while two hypotheses were tested in the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 8,463 (6,751 females and 1,712 males) teachers in the 295 public senior secondary schools Rivers State. The sample size of 846 (675 females and 171 males) teachers was drawn through stratified random sampling technique representing 10% of the population. The face validated Teachers' Continuous Education Management for Enhanced Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (TCEMEIDQ) was used for data collection. Internal consistency reliability through Cronbach alpha gave a coefficient of 0.87 for TCEMEIDQ. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that organization and supervision of teachers to a very high extent can enhance instructional delivery. The researchers recommended that the Ministry of Education and school administrators should demonstrate serious commitment through planning, organizing and supervision of teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Keywords: teachers, continuous education, instructional delivery

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are prominent in the educational setting, this is to say that without the teacher, teaching and learning cannot take place. The teachers' responsibility is to guide the teaching and learning process, as to actualize educational goals, to this effect, teachers in the 21st century are expected not to be timid, they are to be well informed, prepared and professionally minded, research oriented, eager for training and retraining schemes and have utmost commitment with the students and society (Wobo, 2018).

The teacher can only be considered to have taught only when the learner have acquired the prerequisite knowledge and experiences, thus teachers ought to engage themselves in brainstorming, seeking for knowledge and new experiences as to carry out self-audit and criticism on their capacities and practices with the aim of remaining strong on the challenges in the teaching and learning process (Ekwuru and Okonkwo 2017). No wonder obanya (2018) opined, that teachers can reform the educational sector by making the learning process more dynamic, thus bringing a positive change using the available resources. Teachers at one level or the other play an imperative role of planning, organizing, supervising, directing, evaluating and reporting feedback of

educational policies, as well as planning of lesson notes, delivering quality instructional content within the time frame, set exams, supervise and get the feedback from the learner.

The presence of teachers cannot be over emphasized for quality instructional delivery; Obanya, (2018) therefore maintained that, "without an effective teacher there will be no desired change and there will be no access to quality education". The researchers supported the above as they agreed that for teachers to remain academically sound as to influence the learner positively, he must be involved in one professional training or the other, as to equip and abreast himself with the required skills to take charge and control the classroom with the requisite knowledge. Therefore, teachers ought to be engaged through teachers' continuous education as to be informed with the development in the school curriculum and society at large.

Agabi in Wobo and Chuku (2018) defined, continuous education as the classes provided for adults who have finished their education in a range of various subjects. It is seen as an attractive way of acquiring skills, knowledge and acquisitions. Which can be acquired through seminars, workshops, in-service training and more. However, it can also be seen as the type of education that can bring about development of skills in one area of study or the other, it is specifically offered to adults within the community by local school boards and the university.

Graduates or the working class can embark on continuous education programme courses as to upgrade their skills and earn more salaries as well as being more productive and be of value to themselves and society at large; hence, certificates are issued to individuals who successfully complete such programmes. Teachers on the other side, do register for teachers' continuous education TCE which gives them the enablement to meet up with the societal changes where the "generation of z, that is the children born between 1997 -2012" and generation of alpha, children born between 2010 - 2024" those that will see the first phase of the 22nd century (The Collins dictionary, 2020). The alpha generations are digital indigens conversant with the use of 3rd and 4th generation computers.

TCE equips teachers positively as to be up and doing hence the millennials are hungry and eager to search for information on their own if they perceive that the teacher is not relevant (Obong, 2018). It is a programme organized and designed to improve the quality of teachers through development of skills, knowledge and expertise; it records and unveils what the teacher learnt as well as experiences as they apply it in their field to teach more effectively, efficiently and competently as to show case themselves as quality and resourceful teachers. Teachers on the other hand do attend conferences, workshops, seminars, online training, e-learning courses to improve on their strength, develop themselves with a sound minds; although TCE is equally organized by the school administration to help facilitate the teacher. School administrators in the form of the principal, educational managers and planners provide and encourage teachers to register and be part of the training programmes, having fixed the time, as well as provided the venue, facilitators, instructional materials, and other necessary resources (Wobo and Okafor 2017).

In the words of Agabi, (2016) Teachers must be specific, in that they should know what they want to learn as to go for it intensively, the researchers are of the opinion that during the programme, teachers ought to engage themselves with writing materials to write down key points, learn new methods of teaching as to expose the millennials to new knowledge thereafter, be attentive, otherwise, the aim of the programme will be defeated. The researchers insisted that it is not enough for school administrators in the person of the principal, head of school to plan for teachers continuous education, they should as well check the time allocated for such programmes whether it' is worthwhile or not, supervise the teachers on training keenly to ensure they are doing the right thing, this is because, if the programme is well planned, organized, supervised and implemented accordingly, it will bring a positive change on the teacher thus, ascertaining quality instructional delivery. This is why Wordu and Akor (2018) explained that quality instructional delivery is the method the teacher has chosen to relate the content of the subject, instructions or lessons to her students; it is a process that describes what happened in the classroom during the teaching and learning process, however if the teacher employs skills, techniques, procedures or methods while teaching to ensure fruitfulness, and exposes content as well as the evaluation process, it sums up as instructional delivery The Instructional delivery process that will be needed in public secondary schools in Rivers State will be that of teachers who have undergone TCE as they will be relevant in different fields. In the same vein, teachers should equally note that a model of instruction is

not encouraged as they ought to explore different methods while teaching on new experiences and analytical reasoning, as it is stated in the global competitive market, that quality service delivery is a gigantic means of success. Quality service delivery should be guided by some principles such as teachers;

- Meeting educational and societal needs.
- Knowing what to do and how to do it.
- Supporting one another in job description and feedback, conducive working environment, supportive supervision, team work, effective communication through sharing of ideas

Statement of the problem

Research has shown that for teachers to be competent in different fields, they ought to be informed through teachers' continuous education programmes, such as conferences, seminars, workshops, in-service training among others, as these will equip and guide the teacher properly and as well give her the enablement as to adapt with the changing needs of the schools and society, where the millennials are conversant with the use of digital computers as digital indigens. TCE if organized and supervised accordingly by the school administrators in public secondary schools in Rivers State at least once or twice a year, it will prepare and align the teacher to be ethical in the classroom and as well show a great level of competence in the classroom thereby exposing learners with skills and knowledge using different methods. The researchers are bothered and want to find out if Teachers' Continuous Education Management for Enhanced Instructional Delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State is being organized and supervised as planned. This is what the study wants to unravel and solve

Objectives of the study

Based on the problems mentioned above, the objectives are to;

1. Find out the extent supervision of Teachers Continuous Education can Enhance Instructional Delivery in public secondary schools in River State.
2. Identify the extent organization of Teachers Continuous Education can enhance Instructional Delivery in Public Secondary Schools in River State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered

1. To what extent can the supervision of teachers' continuous education enhance Instructional delivery in Public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent can the organization of teachers' continuous education enhance instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of supervision on teachers' continuous education for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of organization for teachers' continuous education for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHOD

The study is a descriptive survey design. The design is suitable because it can describe an ongoing phenomenon on teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State. It researched two research questions and tested two hypotheses. The population of the study comprises 8,463 (6,751 females and 1,712 males) teachers in the 295 public senior secondary schools Rivers State. The sample size of 846 (675 females and 171 males) teachers was drawn through stratified random sampling technique representing 10% of the population. The survey was carried out using an instrument titled "Teachers' Continuous Education Management for Enhanced Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (TCEMEIDQ). The instrument TCEMEIDQ was designed to have two sections. The first section elicited information from the respondents on their gender. The second section was designed to have 15 items with response options of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2) Very Low Extent (1) respectively.

Items with serial numbers 1 to 8 were used to elicit responses on supervision of Teachers Continuous Education for Enhanced Instructional Delivery while items 9 to 15 were used to elicit information on organization of Teachers continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in secondary schools in Rivers State. The instrument TCEMEIDQ was face validated by three experts. One from Measurement and Evaluation and the other two from Educational Management and Administration, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. Rivers State. Internal consistency reliability was done for the instrument through Cronbach alpha which yielded a coefficient of 0.87. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the research questions are Very Low Extent (0.99-1.00), Low Extent (1.10-2.00), High Extent (2.10-2.99) and Very Low Extent (3.00-4.00).

RESULTS

Research question 1: *To what extent can the supervision of Teachers Continuous Education enhance Instructional Delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: mean and standard deviation scores on the extent of supervision on Teachers Continuous Education for Enhanced Instructional Delivery

s/n	Supervision of Teachers Continuous Education for Enhanced Instructional Delivery	Male teachers			Female teachers		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Assessment of teachers' certification through continuous education can enhance instructional delivery	3.43	.50	VHE	2.50	.56	HE
2	Continuous education can assist teachers to set goals for improved instructional delivery	3.27	.45	VHE	2.70	.56	HE
3	Supervision of the continuous education planning process can enhance teachers' instructional delivery	3.43	.50	VHE	3.00	.63	VHE
4	Supervision of attendance rates of teachers in continuous education can enhance instructional delivery	3.40	.49	VHE	3.13	.35	VHE
5	Supervision of the use of instructional aids can enhance teachers' instructional delivery	3.62	.45	VHE	3.23	.35	VHE
6	Supervision of the selection of teachers based on areas on need in continuous education for enhanced teachers' instructional delivery	3.27	.45	VHE	2.83	.35	HE
7	Supervision of selection processes of facilitators can enhance teachers' instructional delivery	3.27	.45	VHE	3.07	.71	VHE
8	Supervision of information management processes in continuous education can lead to effective instructional delivery	3.30	.47	VHE	3.27	.70	VHE
Aggregate mean and standard deviation		3.37	0.47	VHE	2.96	0.53	HE

Very Low Level (0.99-1.00), Low Level (1.10-2.00), High Level (2.10-2.99) and Very Low Level (3.00-4.00).

Table 1 revealed that male teachers have aggregate mean value of 3.37 while the female teachers have 2.96. This revealed that male teachers agreed that supervision of teachers' continuous education to a very high extent can enhance instructional delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State while female teachers agreed to high extent.

Research question 2: *To what extent can the organization on teachers' continuous education enhance instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table: mean and standard deviation of organization on teachers’ continuous education for enhanced instructional delivery

s/n	Organization of Teachers Continuous Education Management for Enhanced Instructional Delivery	Male teachers			Female teachers		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
9	Organization of continuous education during holiday periods can enhance instructional delivery	2.53	.48	HE	3.40	.63	VHE
10	Organization of time for instructional delivery can enhance teachers’ effective instructional delivery	3.13	.50	VHE	3.12	.41	VHE
11	Organization of continuous education venue can enhance teachers’ effective instructional delivery	3.37	.49	VHE	3.20	.41	VHE
12	Organization of reward system for facilitators in continuous education can enhance effective instructional delivery	2.93	.48	HE	3.13	.35	VHE
13	Organization of reward system for teachers in continuous education can enhance effective instructional delivery	3.01	.47	VHE	3.20	.68	VHE
14	Regular organization of continuous education delivery can enhance teachers’ effective instructional delivery	3.27	.45	VHE	3.23	.86	VHE
15	Organization of continuous education based on curriculum can enhance teachers’ effective instructional delivery	2.88	.48	HE	2.74	.51	LE
Aggregate mean and standard deviation		3.02	0.48	VHE	3.15	0.55	VHE

Very Low Level (0.99-1.00), Low Level (1.10-2.00), High Level (2.10-2.99) and Very High Level (3.00-4.00).

Table 2 revealed that male teachers have aggregate mean value of 3.02 while female teachers have mean of 3.15 respectively. Therefore, the result showed that male and female principals agreed that organization of teachers’ continuous education to a very high extent can enhance instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of supervision on teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 3: t-test calculation on the extent of supervision of Teachers Continuous Education for Enhanced Instructional Delivery

Gender	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal.	Sig,	Alpha level	Decision
Male teachers	171	3.37	0.47	844	10.25	.00	.05	Significant
Female teachers	675	2.96	0.53					

Table 3 revealed that male teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.37 and 0.47 while female teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.96 and 0.53 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 844, the calculated t-value of 10.25 is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of supervision on teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of organization for teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test calculation on the extent of organization of Teachers Continuous Education for Enhanced Instructional Delivery

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal.	Sig,	Alpha level	Decision
Male teachers	171	3.04	0.48	844	0.23	.30	.05	Not significant
Female teachers	675	3.15	0.55					

Table 4 revealed that male teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.04 and 0.48 while female teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.15 and 0.55 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 844, the calculated t-value of 0.23 is accepted because the significant value of 0.30 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of organization of teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study are summarized as shown below:

1. The result revealed that male teachers agreed that supervision of teachers' continuous education to a very high extent can enhance instructional delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State while female teachers agreed to high extent. The hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of supervision on teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. The result showed that male and female principals agreed that organization of teachers' continuous education to a very high extent can enhance instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the extent of organization of teachers' continuous education management for enhanced instructional delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Teachers' Continuous education is a business for all, the government at all levels the federal, state, local government, schools, teachers, non-governmental organizations should devise a means to ensure that teachers go for training from time to time as it will enhance quality instructional delivery in public secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Ministry of Education and the principals should ensure that educational policies will set out a different team for the organization and supervision of teachers' continuous education in order to ensure it seamless operation for enhanced instructional delivery.
2. School administrators should ensure that the right teachers are sent for conferences and seminars as it will promote Instructional delivery process.

REFERENCES

- Agabi. O. C. (2006). *The Classroom Communication* in O. G. Agabi & N.C. Okorie (Eds). Classroom Management, Totan Publishers.
- Collins English Dictionary. (2020). *Collins English Dictionary: Complete and Unabridged (10th ed)* Harper Collins.
- Ekwuru, J. C & Okonkwo, O. C (2017). *Issues, Challenges and Prospects of Teaching Profession in the Digital World in the teaching profession & Teaching in a Digital World* (Eds). Williams, Cheta Asodike, J.D Duru, Veronica W.

- Obanya, P. (201 8). Fundamentals of Teacher Education Development Bringing Back the Teacher to the African School. 24th Distinguished Lecture Series, Adeuran Ogunsanya College of Education.
- Obong, M. H. (2018). Managing Knowledge Symbiosis Among Lecturers for Sustainable Higher Delivery in South-South Nigerian Universities. *International Journal of Innovative development and Policy studies*. Vol. 6 (3) July September, 2018. Pp. 16-23.
- Wobo. A.M. (2016). Assessment of the implement of Entrepreneurship Education in Tertiary Institution in Rivers State. An Unpublished Dissertation Presented to University of Port Harcourt Faculty of Education.
- Wobo, A. M, & Okafor. M. U. (201 7). Entrepreneurship Education and Youth Employment in Rivers State. *Rivers State Counselling Association of Nigeria Journal (RIVCASSON)*. Vol 2, No 1.
- Wobo, A. M & Chuku, E. E.(2018). Impact of Management Information System on Effective Human Resources Management in Tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research* 6(2):8-12.
- Wordu, H & Akor, V. O. (2018). Instructional Delivery Models and Academic Performance of Agricultural Science Studies in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*. ISSN 2489- 0733 Vol. (4), No 9.